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Revision History

Revision No.	Effectivity Date	Author	Description of change
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Title: Unlocking Sci-Math Minds: Exploring Classroom Culture with Manipulatives

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Abstract

Educational reforms have been called for to meet the global sustainable development goal on quality education. This much needed reform and the SDG 4 goals have also been aimed on the national level considering our global economic status and our students' standing in international examinations like Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) 2022 and Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2018. This need resonated even more with the similar results on the National Achievement Tests (NAT) which showed students' low positions in both Mathematics and Science among subject areas across Grade 6, 10, and 12 (DepEd, 2019). With these concerns, it is important to revisit and understand classroom culture. This consequently implies the immense role of teachers in the classroom for the much desired educational development. As being said, teachers are essential in improving students' knowledge and skills to achieve the desired goals efficiently (Joshi et al., 2022).

This qualitative-descriptive study aims to explore the Science and Mathematics classroom culture involving manipulatives. Mapping this classroom culture will define the selected science and mathematics junior high school teachers of Nueva Vizcaya teacher's experiences and practices in teaching science and mathematics and will characterize the needed training/ teaching-learning framework for professional development which will be disseminated to the participants and colleagues in the field. The data collection method will consist of semi-structured interview, observation, and document scanning. Thematic analysis and cross-sectional data analysis will be utilized to unveil/ provide a comprehensive understanding of the science and mathematics classroom culture. Ethical considerations will prioritize participant privacy, confidentiality, and emotional well-being. The research outcomes are intended to enhance the educational experiences of junior high school mathematics and science teachers and will be openly shared with the academic community and beyond.

Keywords: transformation, teaching strategies, training needs, professional enhancement

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Introduction

The Sustainable development Goal (SDG 4) on quality education encourages educational reforms focused on lifelong learning opportunities for all. This goal has also been aimed on the national level leading to changes in the curriculum. The much needed modification has been motivated by the global concern and has been emphasized with the unfortunate standing of the Philippines on global Science and Mathematics aptitude tests like in the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) 2022 and in the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2018. This need resonated even more with the similar results on the national achievement tests which revealed Mathematics and Science being significantly the lowest among tested subject areas across Grade 6, 10, and 12 (DepEd, 2019). With these concerns, there is a need to revisit and understand classroom cultures. This also suggests the great role of teachers in the classroom for the much desired educational development. As being said, teachers are essential in improving students' skills as well as knowledge to achieve the desired goals efficiently (Joshi et al., 2022).

Mathematics and Science 21stClassrooms

The 21st century presents significant, multi-faceted, rapid and interdependent challenges and opportunities for all countries of the world, including the Asia-Pacific. These challenges and opportunities lead to the goal of shaping education development-Toward Education for All (EFA) 2015 and Beyond – Shaping a New Vision for Education, in which the education leaders within the region convened for (UNESCO Education Policy and Reform Unit, 2014).

The Philippines is committed to achieving its EFA goals not only for the development of each Filipino, but also for the overall social and economic progress of the country (SEAMEO INNOTECH, 2012). Because of this commitment, the need to translate the sustainable development goals and the demand of regional and global integration, the Department of Education (DepEd) and allied stakeholders implemented a major education reform via its K to 12 program. Educational systems need to innovate to help teachers and students gain 21st-century skills and be actively prepared for the new century (Göçen., Eral, & Bücü, 2020).

The K to 12 Program covers Kindergarten and 12 years of basic education to provide sufficient time for mastery of concepts and skills, develop lifelong learners, and prepare graduates for tertiary education, middle-level skills development, employment, and entrepreneurship (DepEd, 2013). Authors of this curricular reform claim that one salient feature of this transformation is to ensure integrated and seamless learning through spiral progression. Through this approach, concepts and skills in Life Sciences, Physics, Chemistry, Earth Sciences and Mathematics are presented with increasing levels of complexity from one grade level to another, thus paving the way to a deeper understanding of core concepts. The integration across science and mathematics topics and other disciplines will lead to a meaningful understanding of concepts and its application to real-life situation (DepEd, 2013).

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According to UNESCO (2009), teachers are the key players in improving the learning of all our children in school. The large majority of the world's population has experience of being in school and the job of the teacher may seem obvious. However, detailed studies show the complexity of the role of the teacher, especially where the teacher is responsible for the majority or the entire curriculum. Furthermore, teachers are the key to achieving the vision of K to 12 education program. With this high demand for teachers, DepEd will and has to give due consideration and appropriate support to ensure that teachers will be able to fulfill their significant role in the K to 12 education program (SEAMEO INNOTECH, 2012). This assistance will be translated to the classroom.

The pioneers of the K to 12 curriculum claim that the changes are necessary to upgrade the standards of Philippine education (DepEd, 2013). There is truth in the country's status that our basic education is far behind the global educational system. Our students' standing in international or national examinations like TIMSS, PISA and NAT speaks of our position. With these concerns, there is a need to revisit and understand classroom cultures.

Classroom Culture with Manipulative

The classroom culture required by SDG 4 is geared towards lifelong learning opportunities. It is a classroom where the 21st century skills, pedagogical and technological skills are developed shaping students toward enhanced learning leading to critical leadership and creative innovation.

Larbi and Mavis (2016) defined manipulative as materials from the environment that learners can use to learn or form mathematical concepts. Manipulatives are physical objects which are utilized as teaching tool to engage students in hands-on learning of mathematics (Smith, 2009) and science.

Kennedy (1986, as cited by Larbi and Mavis, 2016) defines manipulative as objects that appeal to several senses, these are things that can be touched, moved about, rearranged, and otherwise handled by children. For Fletcher (2009), manipulating familiar objects which inspire confidence is the start of developing a sense of structure in which this structure eventually will emerge in the form of a generalization or expression.

Heddens (1997) claims that manipulatives must be used with care, or else students are made to believe that two mathematical worlds exist; manipulative and symbolic. The use of the manipulatives stimulate learners' interest and promotes active involvement in the learning process (Munger, 2007 as cited by Larbi and Mavis, 2016), help develop mathematical ideas (Heddens, 1997), and enhance performance (Kablan, 2016).

Learning basically occurs when learners interact with the environment and encounter some experiences through which discoveries and relationships are made among concepts (Larbi and Mavis, 2016).

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

Kolb described learning as made up of two dimensions, prehending or grasping information, and transforming or processing that information. The prehending dimension ranges from concrete experience to abstract conceptualization. The transforming

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dimension ranges from reflective observation to active experimentation. Kolb suggested that learning occurs as the individual moves through a cycle of concrete experience [hands-on], reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation (Murrell & Claxton, 1987).

As explained by Roberts (2003), in Dewey's experiential learning theory, everything occurs within a social environment. Knowledge is socially constructed and based on experiences. This knowledge should be organized in real life experiences that provide a context for the information. The teacher's role is to organize this content and to facilitate the actual experiences. The experiences are based on the capabilities and readiness of the learners. The quality of the experience is the most important component of the theory. Upon completion of an experience, learners have the knowledge and the ability to apply it in differing situations. Thus, they have created new knowledge and are at a different level of readiness for continued acquisition and construction of new knowledge.

Several studies (Muhammad, et al., 2023; Ondog & Kilag, 2023; Willingham, 2017; Carbonneau, et al., 2013; Kablan, 2016; Laski, et al., 2015) reveal that manipulatives or hands-on materials aid in enhancing learning, increase engagement, encourage critical thinking and creativity. Students enjoyed doing hands-on/laboratory activities and the experiments help arouse their interest and enhance their comprehension of the pertinent ideas as argued by Kapici et al (2019). Research claims that allowing learners to manipulate physical objects and engage in real-life problem-solving activities facilitate the development of a strong conceptual foundation in science and mathematics.

In this study, manipulatives include materials from the environment for use of students to learn concepts (Larbi & Mavis, 2016) or physical objects use as teaching tools to engage learners (Smith, 2009). This will consider any material for hands-on activities, things that may be set-up/ changed/molded, used for hands-on or laboratory activities, to demonstrate/ learn principles/ equations, and/or create model/ framework. The classroom culture will be examined according to availability, access, sources, sufficiency of these materials, and the teaching experiences and practices in utilizing manipulatives.

Through this study, several benefits await the science and mathematics teachers themselves, who are primary beneficiaries. They will be made aware of their classroom culture involving manipulatives consequently, they will benefit from a professional development program. The study will also be beneficial to the administrators who will lead their science and mathematics teachers in enhancing classroom culture involving manipulatives and can use the same concept for the others teachers of different departments. It will also be beneficial for the students that when their science and mathematics teachers have good classroom culture involving manipulatives, they will learn and feel better in their classes.

Statement of the Objectives:

This study explored the Junior High School Science and Mathematics classroom culture involving manipulatives. Mapping this classroom culture defined the teacher's experiences in teaching science and mathematics and characterized the needed training/

teaching-learning framework which will be disseminated at the end of the academic year 2024-2025 to the participants and colleagues in the field. Specifically, it aimed to

1. describe the teachers' practices in teaching secondary mathematics and science involving manipulatives;
2. identify the challenges encountered in teaching; and
3. design a professional development plan involving manipulatives to address the challenges encountered by the teachers in secondary mathematics and science.

Methodology
Design

In this inquiry, qualitative-descriptive approach was utilized. The science and mathematics classroom culture was explored considering the utilization of manipulatives in teaching lessons/ achieving the required most essential learning competencies (MELC).

Locale

This study was conducted during the academic year 2024-2025 in selected Junior High School in Nueva Vizcaya. It involved three identified schools with low National Achievement Test mean-percentage score (NAT MPS) in both science and mathematics. The recent NAT MPS result was accessed from the School's Division Superintendent of the Department of Education- Division of Nueva Vizcaya.

Participants

Participants of this research were selected purposively from the identified Public High Schools with low National Achievement Test mean-percentage score (NAT MPS) in both science and mathematics. It involved fourteen participants.

Table 1. Number of Respondents

Schools	Respondents
A	4
B	4
C	6
TOTAL	14

The study used the purposive sampling method, specifically targeting mathematics teachers who met the criteria set by the researchers and are actively involved in teaching junior high school science and/or mathematics. This deliberate selection is justified by the need for in-depth insights from experts directly involved in the subject of interest. Purposive sampling ensured that participants possess the required experience in teaching science and/or mathematics, especially with the use of manipulatives. Additionally, it aligns with the study's geographical focus on Nueva Vizcaya.

Table 2. Criteria for Selecting the Respondents of the Study

Criteria	Description
Teaching Experience	A teacher with at least one year of teaching experience in Junior High School.
Subject Expertise	A teacher with a background in science and/or mathematics education.
Current Role	A teacher who actively teaches science and/or mathematics in junior high school during the study period.
Resources	A teacher with access to the utilization of manipulatives for teaching science and/or mathematics.
Willingness	A teacher who is willing to take part in the study actively.

Participants of this research involved fourteen junior high school regular/permanent teachers handling science and/or mathematics subjects, thirteen completed education programs (BSE/Based) and one is a BSCE graduate. The eldest completed his degree in 1998 and has been in service for 26 years, while the youngest completed his degree in 2020 and has been in service for four years.

Among the fourteen teacher respondents, six are mathematics teachers, each of whom handles at least three grade levels. They love math, and they find the subject interesting. The teacher-engineer has embraced teaching the subject because it is closed to his priority program.

The eight science teachers, each of whom handles at least two grade levels, love science, like to explore and they find the subject interesting. They have different specializations – Chemistry, Gen. Science, Biology/ Biological Science, Physical Science and General Science.

D. Research Instruments

Semi-structured interview guide. This guide consists of two parts. The first part (Participant Profile) included seven questions to describe the participants on their educational background and science and mathematics learning experiences. The second part of the interview guide (Teaching Experiences) included five open-ended questions about the utilization, availability, accessibility, sufficiency of, and experiences on the use of manipulatives when teaching the said subjects. Three educator-researchers/ experts were tapped to validate the open-ended questions which provided a comprehensive understanding of the science and mathematics classroom culture. The main questions asked during the interview are indicated in Appendix C.

Observation Checklist/ listing. This included listing of materials as observed in class discussion/ activity. The checklist was patterned according to DepEd classroom observation tool (COT-RPMS Rating Sheet) specifically along the indicator PPST 1.4.2 in

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which the teacher used a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills. (Appendix D. Sample Checklist)

Document Scanning Checklist. Documents scanned included Daily lesson logs (DLL) or lesson plans, student activity sheets/ output, COT-Ratings; Inventory, and/or Means of verification (MOV). These documents were scrutinized on the utilization, availability, accessibility, sufficiency of, and experiences on the use of manipulatives.

Data Gathering Procedure

This study was communicated with the DepEd Division Office, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. Permission was sought from the Schools Division Superintendent for the conduct of the study (Appendix A. Communication Letter). Researchers seek approval of and coordinated with the concerned principals of the selected public schools for some arrangements on needed interview, observation, and document scanning. Consent of the Science and/or Mathematics Teachers who were interviewed and observed were obtained. The researchers visited and conducted the data gathering for two days. All responses and related-data collected were collated and thoughtfully analyzed and interpreted. The responses helped the researchers to better understand the participants which eventually led to mapping the science and mathematics culture involving manipulatives and construct a professional development plan for the participants and colleagues in the field.

Treatment of Data

Thematic analysis was utilized to unveil recurring themes and categories within the participants' responses as they describe their classroom experiences. Cross-sectional data analysis was employed to analyze information from observation and document-scanning checklist. These provided a comprehensive understanding of the classroom culture which defined the teacher's experiences in teaching science and mathematics and characterized the needed training/ teaching-learning framework for professional development.

Part of cross-sectional data analysis to examine the science and mathematics classroom culture according to availability, access, sources, sufficiency of these materials, and the teaching experiences in utilizing manipulatives is presented in Appendix D.

Results and Discussions

- A. Teachers' practices in teaching secondary mathematics and science involving manipulatives;

In exploring the classroom culture of the sci-math teachers involving manipulatives, the teacher-respondents said:

"In my science class, I usually bring my learners to the science laboratory room for them to have first- hand experiences. I also use this strategy to make my learners familiarize themselves to laboratory apparatus for them to relate with during my class interactions."

"In teaching my respective classes, I always do my best so learners will experience Science in our lessons. I allow/let them to observe specimen, focus specimen and make slides in our lesson about cells."

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The science teachers allow their students to observe, sometimes to manipulate laboratory apparatus such as microscope for them to know the anatomy of microscope, to focus specimen, to undergo science observation of specimen; and human torso (systems). These manipulatives are used to help them better understand the lesson.

"In the study of rocks, I ask my students to collect rocks and stones of different types for them to see personally what type of rocks is being described, their characteristics and appearance."

"In Chemistry, we use chemicals and other alternatives especially materials used in the kitchen so that they can recognize the properties of ionic and covalent compound."

"In Physics, we use alcohol lamps, beakers, test tubes as we discuss the lessons on heat transfer. For light, we use mirrors, inks for mixing colors. In teaching electro-magnetic waves, we use water and mirror to see/observe the spectrum instead of the use of prism. We usually use soap (Perla) to represent the different types of plate boundaries. These are some of the topics where we utilize manipulatives because we always believe and want our students to believe that Science is a fun and an exciting subject."

"In the field of mathematics, flash cards are used in performing operations on integers (speed & accuracy). Real life objects are considered in most of the illustrative examples. Damath boards are provided to practice operations on numbers. Maths bingo is sometimes used to motivate students to practice and to master the four fundamental operations. Number line is used in illustrating absolute value and operations on integers."

"In measuring and comparing lengths and distance, we use ruler and metersticks. We use protractors to measure angles. We use protractors in constructing models and presenting theorems on circles that requires proofs. In the absence of clinometer, we use improvised/indigenized clinometer to measure angles of elevation and depression."

"Students are taught how to use the compass during discussions. Compass is used to draw circles & regular polygons. Graphing boards, triangles and geoboards are used for demonstration, however, if time permits, we allow our students to explore."

"For Math 10, we usually use calculators especially when computing complex problems in sequence and polynomials, permutations and combinations. In addition to calculators, we use dice, graphing aids and probability kits in Trigonometry, Probability and Statistics."

The sci-math teachers utilize manipulatives in teaching their subjects. In their undergraduate experiences, 13 out of 14 enjoyed performing hands-on activities and using manipulatives. Laboratory activities/hands-on activities were done in a laboratory room with materials and it is done by group. There were motivational activity sheets. Laboratory activities or hands-on activities were conducted/performed through the use of different chemicals wherein they looked for the unknown elements present in the solution. They used calculators. They manipulated microscopes, experienced making soaps and wine. They also experienced field activities to get specimens (Imugan & Dinadiawan). They enjoyed learning because of these experiences.

Studies indicate that manipulatives and laboratory activities significantly affect the academic performance and development of the process skills of students. Shana and Abulibdeh (2020) showed a positive relationship of manipulatives and laboratory activities

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and the academic performance of students. Additionally, Norona and Abuda (2020) found that the occasional utilization of a few manipulatives and laboratory resources resulted in a very low mastery level of integrated SPS of Grade 11 participants. These findings collectively emphasize the need for regular and practical hands-on experiences to support students' academic development.

Despite the establishment of the positive effect of utilizing manipulatives and laboratory activities in teaching science and mathematics, explorations and hands-on activities are limited due to some factors.

B. Challenges encountered in teaching secondary mathematics and science involving manipulatives

Challenges in the education sector are not new, as issues have persisted from the early years to the present day, particularly in our contexts. Despite the relentless efforts of the DepEd to devise solutions, significant obstacles remain.

Limited resources

One of the significant challenges in sci-math education is the persistent issue of resource limitations. Generally, many of our schools particularly in remote and last mile schools lack access to essential laboratory facilities, equipment, and updated instructional materials necessary for effective science and mathematics teaching. This scarcity restricts learners' opportunities to engage in hands-on experimentation and real-world application of scientific concepts, which are crucial for deep learning. Additionally, limited access to digital tools and online resources further widens the gap, especially in an era where technology-driven learning is becoming the norm. Addressing these resource constraints is critical to creating an equitable and enriching learning environment that empowers learners to develop essential 21st-century science skills (Bibas, 2025).

Among the 14 respondents, 13 claimed that instructional materials are limited. According to Teacher Ann, *"the available equipment/ materials is not enough for the whole class, we need to group the learners for them to manipulate/operate it.* According to Teacher Ben, *"the available manipulatives are sometimes used for demonstration only because of lack of materials. We use five microscopes for a class of 50 or 46. Sometimes, instead of them doing the activities, I just demonstrate it in our class."*

According to Teacher Carla, *"during demonstration or collaborative activities, some materials like chemicals are not available so the objectives of the activity are not attained."* This was affirmed by Teacher Dane when she said, *"the learners cannot learn well the topic if they did not even know how to use manipulatives which are very limited in the classroom."*

The K to 12 program aims to enhance the quality of education and align it with international standards. However, the implementation has been hampered by limited government funding, lengthy procurement processes, and a growing student population that has strained public school infrastructure for decades Christina Chi (2025); outdated

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facilities, and insufficient or even lack of instructional materials (Navarro, 2022; Llego, 2024).

This is also true in the tertiary level, many higher education institutions face challenges related to insufficient infrastructure and limited access to modern instructional materials (Navarro, 2022; Llego, 2024).

Sometimes, the financial burden on teachers who frequently purchase instructional materials out of their own pockets exacerbates this issue. According to Teacher Ella, *“sometimes, I have to buy some of the needed materials for hands-on experiences.”*

“Since the school can only provide limited resources, we require students to have their own calculator and measuring instruments. We also require them to bring needed materials and/or manipulatives available at home”, according to Teacher Fe.

Despite the DepEd's continuous efforts to address challenges in science and mathematics teaching and delivery—such as improving resource allocation—unprecedented gaps persist, leading to recurring issues. Factors such as varying learner learning needs, limited access to advanced learning tools, and external influences like socio-economic disparities contribute to these persistent challenges. These recurring gaps highlight the complexity of achieving equitable and consistent sci-math education outcomes, underscoring the need for sustained innovation, adaptability, and collaboration among all stakeholders to mitigate long-standing and emerging issues.

Time Constraint

Effective use of classroom time is instrumental in an effective classroom management. Time management helps avoid unnecessary deviation and ensure that every minute is utilized efficiently, contributing to a more focused and productive learning experience. The timing of what occurs in the classroom can affect how successfully science and mathematics concepts and skills are learned. For optimal learning, teachers must focus on short, engaging sessions, mixed with active learning activities and breaks to maintain student attention and promote deeper processing and assimilation of information.

Time management allows teachers and students to make the most of their available time, optimizing productivity and efficiency. Students need dedicated instructional time to learn the science and mathematics concepts and skills. Time constraint then is a limiting factor that affects the teaching and learning process. This means that insufficient time to complete all the scheduled tasks within the period or class time affects the quality of teaching and learning. This can arise due to various reasons, such as unavailability of resources.

According to Teacher Ella, *“the 45-minute class time is very challenging. Some*

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microscopes are defective and we carry them from one classroom to another. Time is not maximized, instead of hands-on activities, we usually demonstrate and do the exploration."

Teacher Training Gap

A notable challenge in science education is the teacher training gap, particularly in instrumentation and improvisation. Many schools received science laboratory instruments and math manipulatives deliveries from DepED, however, many sci-math teachers struggle with effectively utilizing scientific instruments and on the other hand, some also find it challenging of creating improvised teaching aids due to insufficient professional development opportunities. This limitation hinders their ability to deliver hands-on, inquiry-based lessons that are critical for fostering learner engagement and understanding. Without adequate training, teachers may rely heavily on theoretical instruction, depriving learners of the experiential learning necessary for mastering complex scientific and mathematical concepts. Bridging this gap is essential to empower teachers with the skills and confidence to enhance science and mathematics education through innovative and resourceful approaches (Bibas, 2025).

Engaging learners effectively requires innovative teaching strategies that make science relevant, interactive, and relatable, fostering curiosity and a deeper connection to the subject. Addressing this challenge is critical to cultivating a lifelong interest in science and its applications.

The spiral approach to curriculum design, where teachers are required to teach all science components—such as biology, chemistry, physics, and earth & environmental science—presents unique challenges in science education. While intended to build progressively deeper understanding, this model often places immense pressure on teachers to master and effectively deliver multiple disciplines, some of which may not be their areas of expertise. Consequently, the quality of instruction may vary, particularly in specialized topics requiring advanced knowledge.

Some of the manipulatives are un-utilized. According to Teacher Helen, *we have not utilized most of the laboratory materials delivered because we do not know how to manipulate especially Physics materials".* This means that despite the availability of materials, some teachers avoid using them for deeper conceptual understanding (De Vera & Balgura, 2023; Ezenwobodo, 2023; Ukobizaba et al., 2021). A number of the science teacher-respondents claimed that they need more trainings in order to be well versed in using such materials; for without adequate trainings, they may struggle to use the manipulatives effectively.

Inadequate Information Dissemination

Information dissemination is the process of spreading information to ensure that concerned individuals have the knowledge they need to make informed decisions and raise awareness. Sufficient information should be provided in accessible and appropriate ways.

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According to Teacher Ike, “we are not aware of the available materials delivered”. His statement implies that they were not informed that there are available equipment and manipulatives. The person(s) in-charge of their resources failed to update and disseminate the information. Effective dissemination and communication are vital to ensure that the use resources are maximized.

C. Proposed Professional Development Program

The findings of this study have implications for a planned and targeted professional development initiative designed to unlock the minds of sci-math teachers in exploring their classroom culture with manipulatives. This study proposes the “**Promoting Resilience through diverse Experience, academic Support, Excogitation, exploring Notion and providing educational Training (PRESENT) Program,**” designed primarily to address the identified challenges in this study.

PROGRAM TITLE: Promoting Resilience through diverse Experience, academic Support, Excogitation, exploring Notion and providing educational Training (PRESENT)

BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE:

This is a research-utilization project which focuses on collaboration of SMU Science and Mathematics Educators with the DepEd Division of Nueva Vizcaya and probable partners in the academe like UST Education partners to share educational experiences, discuss teaching needs and common challenges of the present time, provide support (ideas, solution, and innovation), and offer opportunities and partnership for professional development.

OBJECTIVES:

This project aims to present and provide opportunities for professional/ educational development. Specifically, it aims to offer support through training focused on teaching science and mathematics using manipulatives. It also aspires to

1. build partnership/ network with colleagues in science and mathematics for academic support
2. seek solution to common educational challenges

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- work collaboratively through training/ mentoring/ updating to attain common goal for our learners

TARGET GROUPS:

This project designed to support Science and Mathematics Secondary/ High School Teachers in the province

Professional Development Program Matrix (For Science & Mathematics Teachers)

Activity	Expected date of Completion
First Open Space Discussion	Jan 18, 2025 (and succeeding years; at least once a year)
Planning and Conduct of Training/ Conference	June -July 2025 (and Succeeding years; at least once a year)
MOA for partnership	Dec 2025-Jan 2026

Conclusions

- The sci-math teachers utilize manipulatives in teaching their subjects. The science teachers allow their students to observe, sometimes to explore and manipulate laboratory apparatus such as microscopes and human torso. In the field of mathematics, real life objects are considered in most of the illustrative examples. Flash cards, Damath boards, number line Maths bingo are used to motivate students to practice and to master the four fundamental operations. Ruler, metersticks, protractors, compass, graphing boards, triangles, geoboards dice, graphing aids, probability kits and calculators are used in measuring, computing, modeling and teaching most of the math concepts. Some of them do DIY (Do It Yourself) and improvisation/indigenization of materials.
- Challenges encountered in teaching secondary mathematics and science involving manipulatives include limited resources, time constraint, training gaps and inadequate information dissemination.

3. The "Promoting Resilience through diverse Experience, academic Support, Excogitation, exploring Notion and providing educational Training (PRESENT) Program," was designed to address the identified challenges in this study.

Recommendations

Further study on the teachers' practices in teaching involving manipulatives per grade level may be conducted to have a comprehensive view of the teaching challenges and needs. It is recommended that project PRESENT may be used and sustained to make the presence and support of SMU, science and mathematics educators and trainers with academic partners on the potential professional growth of teachers.

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